

Chemo-physical properties of dysprosium myristate and stearate soaps

S. K. Upadhyay, R. K. Shukla and Govind Sharma*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Engineering & Technology, R. B. S. College, Bichpuri Campus,
Agra-283 105, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract : The chemo-physical properties of dysprosium-myristate and dysprosium stearate soaps in solid state were investigated by IR, X-ray diffraction and TGA measurements. The IR results revealed that the fatty acids exist in dimeric state through hydrogen bonding and dysprosium soaps possess partial ionic character. The X-ray diffraction measurements were used to calculate the long spacings and the results confirmed the double layer structure of dysprosium soaps. The decomposition reaction was found kinetically of zero-order and the values of energy of activation for myristate and stearate were found to be 10.1 and 9.3 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively.

Keywords : Dysprosium soap, thermogravimetric analyses.

The alkali, alkaline earth and transition metal soaps have been thoroughly investigated but the studies on lanthanide and actinide soaps are scarce¹. The studies on the nature and structure of these soaps are of great importance for their use in industries and for explaining their characteristics under different conditions. The present work deals with the infrared, X-ray and thermal studies of dysprosium soaps in solid state and has been initiated with a view to obtain their structural informations in solid state.

Results and discussion

Infrared spectra :

Absorption bands in infrared spectra of dysprosium soaps (myristate and stearate) were assigned and compared with those of the corresponding fatty acids (Table 1). The absorption maxima in the spectra of fatty acids near 2660–2640, 1700, 1410, 950–940, 690, 680 and 550 are associated with the localized carboxyl group of the acid molecule in the dimeric form. The appearance of two absorption bands corresponding to symmetric and antisymmetric stretching vibrations of carboxylate ion near 1452–1420 cm⁻¹, respectively, in the spectra of dysprosium soaps instead of one band of carboxyl frequency near 1700 cm⁻¹ confirms the ionic nature of these soaps. The results show that the fatty acids exist with dimeric structure through hydrogen bonding between carboxyl groups of the two acid molecules whereas dysprosium soaps are ionic in nature and the metal-oxygen bonds in these soaps have ionic character².

X-Ray diffraction pattern of dysprosium soaps have been investigated to characterize the structure of these soaps. The intensities of the diffracted X-rays as a function of the diffraction angle, 2θ , for dysprosium soaps were recorded and the interplanar spacings, d , have been calculated from the positions of the intense peaks using Bragg relationship $n\lambda = 2d \sin \theta$ where λ is the wavelength of the radiation. The calculated spacing together with the relative intensities with respect to the most intense peaks are given in Table 2. The appearance of the diffractions in dysprosium stearate confirms good crystallinity for these soaps. The average planar distance, for dysprosium myristate and stearate are 39.92 and 48.76 Å, respectively. The difference in the observed values of long spacings for dysprosium myristate and stearate is 8.84 Å which corresponds to twice of the length of additional methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) groups in the fatty acid radical constituent of the soap molecules. The values of the long spacings for these soaps are approximately equal to the double of the length of the fatty acid radical of the soap molecules. It is, therefore suggested that the zig-zag chains of fatty acid radicals extended straight forward in these soap molecules.

The observed values of the long spacings for myristate, 39.92 Å and stearate, 48.76 Å of dysprosium are smaller than the calculated dimensions of myristate, 42.0 Å and stearate, 52.0 Å ions from Pauling's* values³ of atomic radii and bond angles and this suggests that the molecular axes of these soaps are somewhat inclined to the basal planes. It is observed that the long spacing peaks are fairly intense while the short spacing peaks are relatively

Table 1. Infrared absorption spectral frequencies (cm⁻¹) with their assignments

Assignments	Myristic acid	Dysprosium myristate	Stearic acid	Dysprosium stearate
CH ₃ , C-H asym. stretch	2960vw	2960w	2960vw	2960w
CH ₂ , C-H asym. stretch	2920vs	2910vs	2920vs	2910vs
CH ₂ , C-H sym. stretch	2855s	2850vs	2850s	2850s
OH, stretch	2640vs	—	2650vs	—
C=O, stretch	1700vs	—	1700vs	—
COO ⁻ , C-O asym. stretch	—	1540w	—	1540w
COO ⁻ C-O sym. stretch	1465ms	1450ms	—	1420ms
CH ₂ , deformation	1465ms	1450ms	—	1550ms
CH ₂ (adjacent to COOH group), deformation	1410w	1410ms	1410vs	1420ms
CH ₃ sym. deformation	1375vw	1380w	1375w	1390w
Progressive bands (CH ₂) twisting and wagging	1350–1090w	1340–1200w	1350–1200w	1340–1180w
CH ₃ , rocking	1110w	1100–1020w	1110w	1108w
OH, out-of-plane deformation	950s	1100–1020w	940m	—
CH ₂ , rocking	720w	754–730ms	930m	754ms
COH, bending mode	690ms	—	690s	—
COOH, wagging mode	550ms	—	550s	—
Dy-O, bond	—	420m	—	415m

vw = very weak, vs = very sharp, s = sharp, m = medium, w = weak.

weak. The values of long spacing for dysprosium soaps are in agreement with the double layer structure of the soaps proposed⁴ in which metal ions are arranged in parallel planes equally spaced in the soap crystal with fully extended zig-zag chains of fatty acid radicals on both sides of each basal plane.

The results of thermogravimetric analysis of dysprosium soaps myristate and stearate show that the final residue is metal oxide and the weights of the residue are in agreement with the theoretically calculated weight of dysprosium oxide from the molecular formulae of the soaps. A white substance is found deposited at the cold part of the sample tube surrounding the sample and it is identified as myristone (m.p. 78 °C) and stearone (m.p. 88.4 °C) in case of dysprosium myristate and stearate; respectively.

The thermal decomposition of dysprosium soaps can be expressed as

The thermogravimetric data have been used to calculate the energy of activation and to find the order of reaction for the decomposition of dysprosium soaps using the equation⁵

$$\Delta \log (dW/dt)/\Delta(\log W_r) = -(E/2.303 R) [\Delta(1/T)/(\log W_r)] + n$$

where, E = energy of activation, R = gas constant, n = order of decomposition reaction, T = temperature on absolute scale, W_r = difference between the total loss and loss in weight at time t , i.e. $W_0 - W_t$ and dW/dt = value of rate of weight loss obtained from the loss in weight vs time curves at appropriate times.

The plots of $[\log (dW/dt)/(\log W_r)]$ vs $[(1/T)/(\log W_r)]$ have been found to be linear with zero intercept. The energy of activation values from the slope ($-E/2.303R$) of the plots are 10.1 and 9.3 kcal mol⁻¹ for myristate and stearate, respectively.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. grade dysprosium myristate and dysprosium stearate soaps were prepared by direct metathesis of corresponding potassium soap with required amount of dysprosium nitrate solution at 50–55 °C under vigorous stirring. The precipitated soap was filtered and washed with distilled water and acetone and recrystallised with methanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction analysis

2θ	$\sin \theta$	$\lambda/2\sin \theta$	d (Å)	N	I/I_{\max}
(a) Dysprosium myristate :					
6.50	0.0567	13.5996	40.7988	3	0.79
8.80	0.0767	10.0497	40.1988	4	0.25
11.20	0.0975	7.9009	39.5045	5	0.27
13.40	0.1167	6.6083	39.6498	6	0.12
15.60	0.1357	5.6808	39.7663	7	0.10
18.00	0.1564	4.9286	39.4288	8	0.05
20.20	0.1754	4.3965	39.5685	9	0.05
21.80	0.1891	4.0773	40.7730	10	0.06
29.70	0.2563	3.0083	39.1079	13	0.04
31.80	0.2740	2.8143	39.4002	14	0.00
44.20	0.3762	2.0493	40.9860	20	0.04
Average value of $d = 39.93$ Å.					
(b) Dysprosium stearate :					
3.60	0.0314	24.5457	49.0914	2	1.00
5.50	0.0479	16.0698	48.2094	3	0.36
7.20	0.0627	12.2789	49.1156	4	0.13
9.20	0.0801	9.6135	48.0675	5	0.12
10.80	0.0941	8.1920	49.1561	6	0.21
20.00	0.1736	4.4400	48.8400	11	0.15
21.70	0.1882	4.0959	49.1508	12	0.25
25.60	0.2215	3.4800	48.7200	14	0.07
33.40	0.2874	2.6830	48.2940	18	0.06
44.40	0.3778	2.0405	48.9720	24	0.06
Average value of $d = 48.76$ Å.					

The infrared spectra of fatty acids and their corresponding dysprosium soaps were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer "Model 577" grating spectrophotometer in the region $4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ using potassium bromide disc method. The X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained with a Richseifert "2002 D" Isodebyeflex Diffractometer using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiations filtered by a nickel foil over the range of diffraction angle, $2\theta = 35^\circ$ to 65° , where θ is Bragg's angle. The thermogravimetric analysis of

dysprosium soaps was carried out by Perkin-Elmer thermogravimetric analyzer TG-S-2 at a constant heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$ and maintaining similar conditions throughout the investigations.

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